

A Quest for the Existence of Bi-Conditional Statements Over the Theory of a Model

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Abstract: Construction of the group of all bi-conditional statements over the theory of a model and discussing its properties and isomorphic forms for the quest and experiments of the existence of the converse of a statement over that model irrespective of its individual proof.

Keywords: Theory of a model, join as a logical connective, group of if statements, non-divisible infinite abelian group, infinite symmetric and permutation groups.

I. INTRODUCTION

In mathematics I think the most familiar and commonly asked question is that ‘ Is the converse holds?’ . Yes its always being necessary to look after the existence of the converse statement after proving any theorem in mathematics. But it will always be a remarkable thing if for any statement we can tell that its converse holds over the respective theory or not without proving it. Here our quest and experiments are basically focused on that using some very basic group theoretic results.

If \mathcal{U} is a model with *card* $\mathcal{U} \geq \aleph_0$ over the language \mathcal{L} , the theory of \mathcal{U} is denoted by $\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}$, is defined to be the set of all sentences of \mathcal{L} (i.e formulas with no free variables) which are true in \mathcal{U} with *card* $\mathcal{U} \geq \aleph_0$. So $\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U} = \{ \sigma \text{ of } \mathcal{L} : \mathcal{U} \models \sigma \}$. Now let $\Omega \subset \mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}$ such that Ω is the set of all $\sigma \in \mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}$ whose converse are also in $\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}$. We are denoting the converse of σ as σ^{-1} . So $\Omega = \{ \sigma \mid \mathcal{U} \models \sigma \wedge \mathcal{U} \models \sigma^{-1} \}$. Now its evident that $\sigma_i \in \Omega$ and $\sigma_j \in \Omega$ then $\sigma_i \wedge \sigma_j \in \Omega$. Actually our intension is to use ‘ \wedge ’ as a binary composition on Ω . Without loss of generality \wedge is both commutative and associative. Now we treat an unique statement $\sigma \in \Omega$ as the identity statement and defined as $\sigma = \text{‘This is this’}$. So let $\sigma_i \in \Omega$ and $\sigma_i^{-1} \in \Omega$ be its converse then $\sigma_i \wedge \sigma_i^{-1} = \sigma \forall \sigma_i \in \Omega$. Here one thing of special attention is that we have not joined the statements by ‘iff’ rather than simply ‘&’. For example we can think $\sigma_i \in \Omega$, such that $\sigma_i = \text{‘this is X’}$ and $\sigma_i^{-1} = \text{‘X is this’}$, then $\sigma_i \wedge \sigma_i^{-1} = \sigma = \text{‘This is this’}$. With the help of the underlying transitivity. In the same way we can treat other bi-conditional sentences also, for example $\Omega \subset \mathbf{Th} \mathbb{R}$ and let $\sigma_i \in \Omega$ where σ_i stands for ‘closed and bounded subsets of \mathbb{R} are compact subsets of \mathbb{R} ’. Now σ_i^{-1} i.e ‘compact subsets of \mathbb{R} are closed and bounded subsets of \mathbb{R} ’ will also be in Ω . Now if we treat the clause ‘closed and bounded subsets of \mathbb{R} ’ as ‘This’ and ‘compact subsets of \mathbb{R} ’ as ‘X’ then we get $\sigma_i = \text{‘this is X’}$, and $\sigma_i^{-1} = \text{‘X is this’}$; and evidently we get $\sigma_i \wedge \sigma_i^{-1} = \sigma = \text{‘This is this’}$. We will see all sentences like ‘Y is Y’ or ‘Y=Y’ is as same as the identity statement $\sigma = \text{‘This is this’}$. So (Ω, \wedge) be an abelian group. Also note that in (Ω, \wedge) , if $\sigma_i \neq \sigma_j$ then $\sigma_i \wedge \sigma_j = \sigma_i^2 \neq \sigma_i$. From here we will do only some basic group theories and try to connect the desired results for further need of model theory.

Some special properties of the group (Ω, \wedge) :

1. (Ω, \wedge) is torsion free according to its construction.
2. (Ω, \wedge) is always infinite since its torsion free.
3. (Ω, \wedge) is non trivial Abelian so (Ω, \wedge) is not a free group.
4. (Ω, \wedge) has no non trivial finite subgroup because its torsion free and abelian.
5. (Ω, \wedge) is not finitely generated because by the theorem ‘ A finitely generated abelian group is free iff its torsion free’.
6. (Ω, \wedge) is not divisible.

II. OBSERVATION

According to such properties there will not be any chance that (Ω, \wedge) is similar to some of our known groups, even its not isomorphic to groups like (\mathbb{Q}^*, \cdot) or (\mathbb{R}^*, \cdot) etc, according to $o(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$. Because they have finite subgroups. But there

might be possibility that it can be similar with $(\mathbb{Q}^*/\{-1,1\},.)$ or $(\mathbb{R}^*/\{-1,1\},.)$ etc. This observation leads us to go on our further quest and experiments.

Theorem: The group Ω is isomorphic to a subgroup of the symmetric group of $\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}$.

Proof: Let Ω acts on $\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}$. thus for each $\sigma_i \in \Omega$ we can get a bijection $\psi_{\sigma_i} : \mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}$ defined as $\psi_{\sigma_i}(a) = \sigma_i \wedge a$. Along with that there will be an associate homomorphism $\Sigma : \Omega \rightarrow \text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$, where $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$ stands for the symmetric group of $\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}$ with $\Sigma(\sigma_i) = \psi_{\sigma_i}$. So, $\Sigma = \{ \sigma_i \in \Omega \mid \Sigma(\sigma_i) = \psi_{\sigma_i} \}$ where ψ_{σ_i} be the identity map. Therefore by isomorphism theorem $\Omega / \text{Ker} \Sigma$ is isomorphic into $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$. Now claiming that $\text{Ker} \Sigma = \{ \sigma \}$, because if $\sigma_i \in \text{Ker} \Sigma$ then $\Sigma(\sigma_i) = \psi_{\sigma_i}$ where $\psi_{\sigma_i}(a) = \sigma_i \wedge a = a \quad \forall a \in \mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}$. So $\sigma_i = \sigma$. So $\Sigma : \Omega \rightarrow \text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$ is an isomorphism. Since Ω is abelian and Σ is not an onto isomorphism so $\Sigma(\Omega)$ is an abelian subgroup of $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$ of $\mathbf{o}(\Omega)$. The above result is an immediate consequence of Cayley's theorem which states that every group is isomorphic to some permutation group.

Now our work will be to predict the exact structure of $\Sigma(\Omega)$. Because if we are able find any permutation ψ_{σ_i} in $\Sigma(\Omega)$ then at a glance we are also able to say that σ_i^{-1} is also true in \mathcal{U} . We note this as a corollary,

Corollary: If $\psi_{\sigma_i} \in \Sigma(\Omega)$ then $\mathcal{U} \models \sigma_i^{-1}$

To focus on our central problem i.e on $\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}$ if a statement is true then how to predict that its converse is also true or not without proving it; we will now electrify on the abelian subgroups of $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$ since Ω is abelian and isomorphic to a subgroup of $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$. Thus $\Sigma(\Omega)$ enjoys the same group theoretic properties as (Ω, \wedge) . Its evident that $\text{Alt}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$ is obviously a normal subgroup of $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$. But its simple also. Since $\Sigma(\Omega)$ is abelian and not finitely generated so $\Sigma(\Omega)$ can't be simple, thus there will be no question to compare $\Sigma(\Omega)$ and $\text{Alt}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$. Therefore we have to look about some else subgroups of $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$.

Let A be any infinite cardinal number, if $\varphi \in \text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$ then the set $S(\varphi) = \{ \sigma \in \mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U} \mid \varphi(\sigma) \neq \sigma \}$. Now we will define $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}, A) = \{ \varphi \in \text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}) : \mathbf{o}(S(\varphi)) < A \}$. It's easy to verify that $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}, A)$ is a normal subgroup of $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$. For our further experiments we will prefer $A = \aleph_0$.

Theorem: If G is an infinite subgroup of $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}, \aleph_0)$ and $k \in \mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}$ then the order of the stabilizer of k is equals to the order of G .

Proof: Let $G_k = \{ x \in G \mid kx = x \}$ and $\mathbf{o}(G_k) \neq \mathbf{o}(G)$ with all the above conditions. Now let T_k be the orbit of G containing k . So, $\mathbf{o}(G) = \mathbf{o}(G_k)\mathbf{o}(T_k)$. Thus according to our assumption, $\mathbf{o}(T_k) = \mathbf{o}(G)$. (As cardinal arithmetic). Now $\exists g \in G$ such that $gk \neq k$. If $b \in T_k$ then $\exists h \in G$ such that $kh = b$. thus $b \in S(h^{-1}gh)$ as $h^{-1}ghb \neq b$. Therefore, $T_k \subset \cup S(h^{-1}gh)$. Since each $S(h^{-1}gh)$ has same finite order say n and $\mathbf{o}(T_k) = \mathbf{o}(G)$, so g has $\mathbf{o}(G)$ numbers of conjugates. Also $b \in T_k$ then G_b is conjugate to G_k . Hence $\mathbf{o}(G_b) < \mathbf{o}(G)$. So there are $n+1$ distinct elements k_1, \dots, k_{n+1} of T_k . Since each conjugate of g and moves exactly n elements so they will be in some G_{k_i} . Thus $\mathbf{o}(G) \leq \sum(G_{k_i}) = (n+1)\mathbf{o}(G_k) < \mathbf{o}(G)$, Which is a contradiction.

Corollary: If G is an infinite subgroup of $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}, \aleph_0)$ then there exist a proper sub group H of G such that $\mathbf{o}(H) = \mathbf{o}(G)$.

Corollary(ii): If G is an infinite subgroup of $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}, \aleph_0)$ and H is an abelian subgroup of G then there is an abelian subgroup K of G such that $H \subset K$ and $\mathbf{o}(K) = \mathbf{o}(G)$.

Proof: By Zorn's lemma in G there will be a maximal abelian proper subgroup K such that $H \subset K$. As we know that as G is infinite and $U \subset G$ and $\mathbf{o}(U) < \mathbf{o}(G)$, then $\mathbf{o}(C(U)) = \mathbf{o}(G)$. Now if we put $K = U$ so we get $\mathbf{o}(C(U)) = \mathbf{o}(G)$. Hence $\exists x \in C(K)/K$ such that $\langle K, x \rangle$ be abelian, which is a contradiction. So $\mathbf{o}(K) = \mathbf{o}(G)$.

Corollary (iii): If G is an uncountable Abelian group, then G has a well-ordered descending chain of subgroups of length $\mathbf{o}(G)$.

We are skipping the proof here though we can find the proof in the following book*

#Thus if $\Sigma(\Omega)$ or Ω are of order greater than \aleph_0 then they have a well-ordered descending chain of subgroups of length $\mathbf{o}(\Omega)$.

Lemma. Let N be a nontrivial normal subgroup of $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$. Then either $N = \text{Alt}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$ or $N \geq \text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}, \aleph_0)$. (i.e $N = \text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}, \aleph_i)$, for some $i \in \mathbb{N}$)

We are skipping the proof here though we can find the proof in the following book**

Now let $\mathbf{o}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})^+$ be the next higher cardinal after just $\mathbf{o}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$, so we can see that $\text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}, \mathbf{o}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})^+) = \text{Sym}(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$. Thus by the previous lemma we are getting-

Lemma: $\Sigma(\Omega)$ is not a normal subgroup of $Sym(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$.

Proof: its already verified that $\Sigma(\Omega) \neq Alt(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$, again by our previous lemma its clear that $Alt(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$ is also a normal subgroup of $Sym(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}, \aleph_0)$. Which is also true for any c , such that $\aleph_0 < c < o(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})^+$. Since $Alt(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$ is non abelian by corollary (ii).

#So we have to check other sub groups of $Sym(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$ rather than $Alt(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})$ and $Sym(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U}, b)$, with $\aleph_0 \leq b < o(\mathbf{Th} \mathcal{U})^+$.

III. CONCLUSION

Here we are halting our quest because the classification of infinitely generated abelian groups is far from complete, i.e at present it's an open problem. Though there is a complete classification of divisible abelian groups and torsion abelian groups but these are absolutely not fulfilled our present requirement. Though we had proceed to some filtered result and might be the help of computer algorithms and programs we can continue our further quest.

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